

Supplement S1. TRIPOD+AI reporting checklist

Reporting follows the TRIPOD+AI statement for clinical prediction models that use regression or machine learning methods (Collins GS, et al. *BMJ*. 2024;385:e078378). Item text is abbreviated; locations refer to sections of the main manuscript unless a supplement is named. This study developed and internally validated a single model and additionally tested it, without retraining or recalibration, on an external survey year (BRFSS 2022; Supplement S5); items that concern a separate external evaluation dataset point to that temporal test where it applies, and items with no counterpart in this design are marked “Not applicable (internal validation).”

Item	Topic	Reported in
1	Title identifies the study as developing a prediction model, the target population, and the predicted outcome	Title
2	Structured abstract (TRIPOD for Abstracts)	Abstract
3a	Healthcare context and rationale; prognostic prediction of screening nonadherence	Introduction, paragraphs 1-3
3b	Target population and intended use in the care pathway (risk stratification for targeted outreach)	Introduction, paragraphs 1 and 5
3c	Known health inequalities between sociodemographic groups	Introduction, paragraph 1
4	Study objectives; development with internal validation	Introduction, final paragraph

Item	Topic	Reported in
5a	Sources of data for development and evaluation	Methods, Data source and study population; single source with internal cross-validation
5b	Dates of participant data	Methods, Data source (2024 BRFSS cycle); Survey year
6a	Key elements of the study setting	Methods, Study design and reporting; Data source (general adult population, telephone survey)
6b	Eligibility criteria for participants	Methods, Data source and study population
6c	Treatments received and their handling	Not applicable (observational survey; no intervention)
7	Data pre-processing and quality checking, including consistency across sociodemographic groups	Methods, Missing data and survey weights; equity audit checks model behavior across race/ethnicity, income, and insurance
8a	Outcome definition and time horizon	Methods, Outcome (cross-sectional prevalent delay; no follow-up horizon)
8b	Qualifications for subjective outcome assessment	Not applicable; outcome is a CDC-calculated variable from self-report

Item	Topic	Reported in
8c	Blinding of outcome assessment	Not applicable; registry-derived outcome
9a	Choice of initial predictors	Methods, Predictors (a priori from fundamental cause theory)
9b	Definition and measurement of all predictors	Methods, Predictors; variable crosswalk in repository
9c	Qualifications for subjective predictor assessment	Not applicable; predictors are self-reported survey items
10	How study size was arrived at	Methods, Data source (full eligible sample analyzed; no a priori sample-size calculation for this secondary analysis)
11	Handling of missing data	Methods, Missing data and survey weights (in-fold survey-weighted imputation)
12a	How the data were used for development and evaluation	Methods, Validation and performance (nested cross-validation; pooled out-of-fold predictions)
12b	How predictors were handled in the analyses	Methods, Prediction models (one-hot encoding; restricted cubic spline for age)

Item	Topic	Reported in
12c	Model type, rationale, building steps, hyperparameter tuning	Methods, Prediction models and Validation; full search grid in Supplement S4
12d	Handling of heterogeneity in parameter and performance estimates	Methods, Validation (across-fold reporting; design-based bootstrap)
12e	Performance measures and plots, with rationale	Methods, Validation (weighted AUC, weighted Brier, calibration intercept/slope and plot, decision curve analysis)
12f	Model updating such as recalibration	Not performed; stated in Methods, Prediction models
12g	How predictions were calculated for evaluation	Methods, Validation (pooled out-of-fold predicted probabilities)
13	Class-imbalance methods	Methods, Prediction models (no class balancing applied; survey weights only)
14	Approaches to model fairness and rationale	Methods, Validation (within-subgroup discrimination and calibration by race/ethnicity, income, insurance)

Item	Topic	Reported in
15	Output of the prediction model	Predicted probability of screening delay; Methods, Prediction models
16	Differences between development and evaluation data in setting	Supplement S5, External temporal validation (BRFSS 2022); setting differs in survey year, with predictors and outcome recoded to the 2024 schema (Supplement S4)
17	Ethics approval	Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics (IRB exemption; public de-identified data)
18a	Funding source and role of funders	Title page, Funding statement
18b	Conflicts of interest	Title page, Conflict of interest statement
18c	Study protocol access	Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics; analysis pipeline and Decision Log in the public repository
18d	Registration	Not registered; secondary analysis of public-use data (Title page)

Item	Topic	Reported in
18e	Availability of study data	Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics (BRFSS public-use files from CDC)
18f	Availability of analytical code	Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics (code openly available)
19	Patient and public involvement	None; secondary analysis of de-identified public data (Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics)
20a	Flow of participants, with and without the outcome	Results, Sample and outcome (analytic flow); participant flow figure in repository
20b	Characteristics overall and by setting	Results, Sample characteristics (Table 1)
20c	Comparison of predictor distributions across development and evaluation data	Supplement S5 (external temporal validation): 2022 predictors recoded to the 2024 schema and outcome prevalence compared across years; full predictor-distribution tables not produced for the temporal test

Item	Topic	Reported in
21	Number of participants and outcome events per analysis	Results, Sample and outcome; Model performance (n and weighted prevalence per cohort and analysis)
22	Full prediction model	Trained model object and code in the public repository
23a	Performance estimates with confidence intervals, including key subgroups	Results, Model performance and Equity across social groups (Table 2; Figure 3)
23b	Heterogeneity in performance across clusters	Results, Equity across social groups (within-subgroup AUC and calibration; across-fold range)
24	Results from model updating	Not applicable (no updating)
25	Overall interpretation, including fairness	Discussion, Principal findings; Interpretation and mechanisms; Strengths and limitations
26	Study limitations	Discussion, Strengths and limitations
27a	Handling of poor-quality or unavailable input data	Discussion, Strengths and limitations (self-report and reduced-coverage items); Methods, Missing data and survey weights

Item	Topic	Reported in
27b	User interaction in handling input data or model use	Discussion, Interpretation and mechanisms; Conclusions (programmatic use for outreach ranking)
27c	Next steps for future research, applicability, generalizability	Discussion, Strengths and limitations (transportability across survey years; prospective and geographic external validation; period-specific recalibration); Conclusions (quantitative-intersectionality extension)